

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE KEY FEATURES OF A CROWD AS A DISCOURSE COMMUNITY IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

Research on crowds as discourse communities examines the unique linguistic behaviors and social dynamics within large groups. This study, building on foundational works by Foucault, Hymes, and Swales, explores how language evolves in crowds, emphasizing their unstructured, transient nature, and emotional intensity. By analyzing crowd communication patterns, this research contributes to modern linguistics, offering insights into collective behavior and informing interdisciplinary approaches to crowd management and social interaction.

Keywords: crowd, discourse, discourse community, communicative event, national security.

Research on crowds, which began in the 19th century and continues actively into the 21st century, has drawn significant interest to the study of the crowd as a discourse community. Scholars have examined various aspects of crowd behavior, communication patterns, and the social dynamics that influence collective actions. This ongoing research has revealed how crowds form unique linguistic and social structures, contributing valuable insights to the fields of linguistics and sociolinguistics. Understanding these patterns is crucial for comprehending how language and communication evolve within large, often transient, groups of people.

The chosen topic's relevance is closely related to modern language research trends and its aim to develop a holistic understanding of crowds as discourse communities. This focus ensures that the study is both timely and significant, addressing current scholarly interests in how language functions within large social groups. By examining the unique linguistic behaviors and communication patterns of crowds, this research contributes to a deeper comprehension of social dynamics and collective identities. Furthermore, it opens new ways for interdisciplinary studies, linking linguistics with sociology, psychology, and communication studies.

A review of theoretical sources on the research topic has highlighted that, while many aspects have been deeply studied, there are still significant gaps that need to be addressed and comprehensively described. The foundational works of international scholars, such as Michel Foucault's studies on discourse [1] and Dell Hymes' theory of speech communities, have been instrumental in shaping the concept of a "discourse community." [2] However, it was John Swales who first articulated the paradigm for studying discourse communities in a systematic way. His contributions laid the groundwork for further exploration and understanding of how discourse communities' function and evolve, thus emphasizing the importance of this research area. [3]

Since the early 20th century, the phenomenon of crowds has captured the attention of various scientific disciplines, such as psychology [5, 6, 7], sociology [8,

9], and linguistics [1, 2, 4, 10]. This interdisciplinary focus highlights the complex nature of crowds and their significance in contemporary research. The importance of studying crowds has grown exponentially, making it a crucial area of inquiry in modern science. Pioneering figures in this field include G. Le Bon, G. Tarde, S. Freud, E. Fromm, M. Horkheimer, and S. Moscovici, whose foundational work has laid the groundwork for current studies.

In recent years, the study of crowds has been further advanced by prominent Ukrainian researchers such as L. Pelepeichenko and L. Kompantseva. These scholars have contributed to a deeper understanding of the dynamics, behaviors, and linguistic patterns within crowds. Their work underscores the ongoing relevance and complexity of crowd phenomena, providing valuable insights into how individuals interact and communicate within large groups. This growing body of research continues to reveal the multifaceted nature of crowds, emphasizing their importance in both theoretical and practical applications across various fields.

The purpose of this article is to explore and delineate the typical characteristics of a crowd as a discourse community within the framework of modern linguistics. By examining the unique linguistic behaviors and communication patterns that define crowds, this study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how language functions and evolves in large, often transient, social groups. The research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the social dynamics and discourse strategies employed by crowds, highlighting their significance in the broader context of modern linguistic studies.

For this research, the definition of a crowd proposed by Wijermans is relevant: "Crowd is a group of individuals at the same physical location at the same time" [11]. Also, Vincent Price in order to tell the difference between crowd and masses says that "Crowds are defined by their shared emotional experiences, but masses are defined by their interpersonal isolation" [12, p. 12].

MacIver and Page define crowd as “A physically compact aggregation of human beings brought into direct, temporary, and unorganized contact with one another. It is quickly created and quickly dissolved”. According to Lundberg and others, “A crowd is a temporary collection of persons who react to a common focus of attention and engage in spontaneous interaction”. [13]

It is important to note that a crowd is not merely a “mechanical” gathering of people in one place, but a group of individuals united not by territorial or ethnic characteristics, but by common communicative goals. This includes a shared technology, level of competence, knowledge of the genre-specific organization of information, and mechanisms of its exchange. The following features of the crowd may include: 1) increased group suggestibility; 2) heightened emotional perception of reality; 3) diminished sense of responsibility for one's own behavior; and 4) a sense of power and awareness of anonymity [10, p. 103].

The following general characteristics of a crowd are used by most crowd researchers:

- 1) It is unorganized, it has no structure.
- 2) Crowd is transitory and unstable.
- 3) The role of leader is important in a crowd. Especially in an active crowd of the mob type, as is the leader *who* will direct and guide the crowds' action. It has physical presence of a large number of people.
- 4) It has physical presence of a large number of people.
- 5) A crowd, especially of the active type, should have a focus of attention. It may be an accident spot, a person, or even an idea as we find in a revolutionary crowd. [13]

L. Pelepeichenko identifies four main types of crowds:

1. An occasional or accidental crowd arises spontaneously in response to a particular event; it combines elements of organization and spontaneity (a case where the crowd was organized externally, and then the process of self-organization began).
2. A conventional crowd is associated with interest in some pre-announced mass entertainment (sports competitions, concerts). It has a common interest and follows predetermined temporary norms of behavior.
3. An expressive crowd jointly expresses a general attitude towards an event (joy, enthusiasm, indignation, protest).
4. An acting crowd can appear in one of four subtypes: a) aggressive – united by blind hatred towards a particular object; b) panic – spontaneously fleeing from a real or imagined source of danger; c) acquisitive – engaging in unorganized immediate conflict over possession of any values; d) rebellious – where people are united by common just indignation towards the actions of the authorities; it often forms the basis of revolutionary upheavals. [10, p. 105].

G. Le Bon regards any community of people as a crowd or group. In his classification of crowds, he differentiates between homogeneous groups (composed of individuals from the same social class, age group, or

gender) and heterogeneous groups (consisting of members from various social backgrounds identified by distinct characteristics) [5].

Regarding public order, crowds are categorized as: 1) *Loyal (normative)* (these crowds engage in activities that involve upholding, endorsing, and supporting public order; 2) *Protest*: (these crowds partake in activities aimed at challenging or undermining public order; 3) *Neutral (indifferent)* (these crowds do not have a direct effect on public order, such as a crowd of spectators). [10, p. 147]

Le Bon's analysis emphasizes the diverse nature of crowd dynamics and their impact on society. Loyal crowds contribute positively to social stability, reinforcing societal norms and regulations. In contrast, protest crowds can drive social change by voicing dissent and challenging existing structures. Neutral crowds, while not directly affecting public order, can still play a role in shaping social perceptions through their passive presence. Understanding these distinctions is crucial for analyzing social movements and public behavior in various contexts.

All these observations indicate that any crowd is characterized by a shared emotional state and spontaneous behavioral tendencies, along with an increasing psychological contagion – the spread of heightened emotions from one individual to another on a mental level. The absence of clear goals and organizational structure can sometimes make the crowd a target for manipulation or transform it into a tool for exerting pressure and engaging in unlawful actions.

A crowd can be seen as a discursive community. John Swales proposed the characteristics of such communities [3]. Understanding a crowd as a discursive community means recognizing the shared communication practices and common purposes that bind its members together. This approach underscores the role of communication in shaping the crowd's collective behavior, highlighting its potential for both positive social movements and negative manipulative influences.

Drawing on his approach, let's identify the categorical characteristics of a crowd as a discursive community:

1. A group of people that spontaneously forms due to shared interests;
2. Crowds do not always have mechanisms for communication among their members;
3. Some types of crowds create opportunities for information exchange (conventional, organized crowds);
4. Crowds can fully submit to emotions and are susceptible to manipulative influence;
5. The use of special means to manage emotional states (speeches by speakers, music, choral singing, ritual dances, rhythms, various visual stimuli such as flags, symbols, portraits), participants in the crowd filming themselves and broadcasting images on networks.

In the context of crowd discourse, several key elements can be identified:

- The communicator, who initiates informational processes.

- The event, which serves as the informational trigger leading to the formation of the crowd.
- Channels through which information is transmitted.
- The audience, which receives and potentially provides feedback on the information.
- Contact points that facilitate interaction among communicators within the crowd.

As crowds form as intricate communicative events, they manifest at least four types of positioning:

1. Among participants collectively addressing and targeting a recipient, even in the absence of direct contact.
2. Between a leader and the crowd, involving asymmetric interaction dynamics.
3. Between individual participants and the intended recipient.
4. Among participants within the crowd itself.

Each type of positioning serves different communicative purposes. While the first type lacks direct contact with the recipient, it aims to influence nonetheless. The influence's potency often correlates with the number of voices endorsing a collective address by the crowd.

The second type involves communication between a leader addressing the crowd from a podium, characterized by its inherent asymmetry. The speaker aims to secure support, while the crowd, acting as a collective recipient, has limited communicative abilities: they may express support through chants, direct responses of approval or disapproval, chanting slogans, or refraining from communication in a subordinate position. The strength of this interaction lies in its unity, which can exert a powerful influence and make a striking impression on observers, effectively conveying messages to the intended recipient.

The third type of positioning occurs between each participant in the crowd and the intended recipient. Each participant delivers their message on equal terms without a hierarchical structure, fostering informal communication that blurs the lines between formal and informal discourse [1, 14]. The goal for each participant is to ultimately be noticed and heard by the recipient, using self-expression as their strategy. The diverse voices with varied tones and registers create a polyphony of protest, preserving individuality within the collective expression.

The fourth type involves direct communication among demonstrators within the crowd. This type of interaction fosters solidarity among peers, characterized by mutual support, emotional expression, and shared humor. The aim of such communication is to build a community of supporters and like-minded individuals united in solidarity.

The concept of a "discursive community" not only facilitates interdisciplinary research but also addresses crucial challenges such as crowd behavior management for specialists from security and defence institutions. Crowds are composed of diverse communities that may have conflicting interests, needs, and societal roles. Effective communication within such contexts requires

identifying shared objectives and using clear, accessible language to ensure all participants understand the information equally during communicative events.

Further exploration in this field promises to enhance our understanding of crowd dynamics and discourse characteristics within contemporary linguistics. This research can contribute valuable insights into how language and communication strategies influence crowd behavior and societal interactions. Additionally, it can inform the development of effective strategies for crowd control, ensuring safety and order in various public settings. By studying these aspects, researchers can develop comprehensive approaches to manage and mitigate potential risks associated with crowd gatherings.

References

1. Foucault: Power, Discourse, and the State. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304645370_Foucault_Power_Discourse_and_the_State/link/5c05769e92851c6ca1fc20eb/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIn19
2. Hymes, Dell. *Ethnography, Linguistics, Narrative Inequality: Toward an Understanding of Voice*. URL: https://www.academia.edu/60215465/Ethnography_linguistics_narrative_inequality_Toward_an_understanding_of_voice
3. Swales, J.M. Discourse Communities, genres and English as an international language. *World Englishes*, Vol. # 2, 1988. pp. 211-220.
4. Компанцева Л.Ф. Соціальні комунікації для фахівців сектору безпеки та оборони. підруч.: у 2 т. Т.1. К.: Нац. акад. СБУ, 2016. 476 с.
5. Le Bon, Gustave. *The crowd: A study of the popular mind*. URL: <https://www.gutenberg.org/cache/epub/445/pg445-images.html>
6. Freud, Sigmund. *Group Psychology and The Analysis of The Ego*. URL: <https://www.gutenberg.org/cache/epub/35877/pg35877-images.html>
7. Moscovici, S. (1981). *The Age of the Crowd: A Historical Treatise of Mass Psychology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 408 pages.
8. Blumer, Herbert. *Symbolic Interactionism: Perspective and Method*. URL: <https://books.google.com.ua/books?id=HVuognZFofoC&printsec=frontcover&hl=ru#v=onepage&q&f=false>
9. Durkheim, Emile. *The Division of Labor in Society*. URL: https://books.google.com.ua/books?id=B955X3C-9E8C&printsec=frontcover&hl=id&source=gb_s_ummmary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false
10. Мовна комунікація в діяльності сил охорони правопорядка. Теоретичні засади галузевої комунікації [моногр.] За редакцією докт. філолог. наук, проф. Л. М. Пелепейченко. Харків : АБВ МВС України, 2009. 272 с.
11. Wijkers, F. E. H. *Understanding Crowd*

Behaviour: Simulating Situated Individuals. University of Groningen, SOM Research School.

12. Public Opinion. (3 Sept. 2004) Carroll J. Glynn, Susan Herbst, Garrett J. O'Keefe, Robert Y. Shapiro. Publisher: Westview Press; 2nd edition. 510 pages.

13. Social Identity, Crowding and Crowd Behaviour. URL:

<https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/20888/1/Unit-3.pdf>

14. Pramoolsook, I. A Multi-layered Discourse Community: Defining Biotechnology and Environmental Engineering Discourse Communities at SUT. Suranaree J. Soc. Vol. 2, #1. June 2008, pp. 85-97.